

Studies on Optical Activity and Chemical Constitution. Part III. Optically Active Acids and Bases.

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Rule (J. Chem. Soc., 1927, 54) has shown that optically active menthyl and *sec*- β -octyl esters of acetic acid and *ortho*-substituted benzoic acids, containing basic substituents, have relatively low rotatory powers, which rise when the compounds are examined in the form of their hydrochlorides. The following values are recorded in the case of free amines and their hydrochlorides (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 330).

It has been suggested that in the case of monosubstituted acetic acids the structural changes occur at a considerable distance from the optically active group and the effect on the rotatory power is, therefore, small.

This paper deals with the preparation and the optical rotatory powers of 2', 3'- and 4'-dimethylaminocamphoranilic acids. The following table records the rotatory powers of 2'-camphoranilic acids.

TABLE I.

[α] _D in methyl alcohol.						
CO ₂ H*	OH‡	NMe ₂	OMe‡	Cl†	Me†	H†
-157°	-12.6°	0°	9.0°	18.7°	50.5°	57.5°

It would be seen that the dimethylamino group has lowered the rotation of the original compound considerably.

2'-Dimethylaminocamphoranilic acid is an example of an optically active amino-acid, and the substance was examined in the presence

* *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1966.

† *Ibid.*, 1927, 1995.

‡ *Ibid.*, 1930, 1207.

of an equivalent amount of alkali and also with an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid. It has a slight positive rotation in the neutral medium, which increased very little when examined in the presence of alkali, but the rotatory power increased enormously when an equivalent weight of the acid was added.

The following values with and without the addition of hydrochloric acid will be found interesting.

TABLE II.

$\lambda =$	5893	5780	5461	4359
Neutral medium	0°	6.2°	8.12°	18.70
1 mol HCl	55.52	57.02	68.52	118.54

The marked changes in the rotatory power may be attributed to the fact that the group of electrons which gives rise to optical rotatory power is considerably modified (*cf.* J. Liquier Milward, *Ann. Physique*, 1927, 8, 121).

The dimethylamino group in the 4'-position has, however, raised the rotatory power of the original compound but not to the extent as was expected. This effect of the alkylamino group in the 4'-position has already been shown in the case of dimethyl and diethylamino-phenyliminocamphors (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 219, 768):

The 4'-dimethylamino acid was also examined in the presence of an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid and then in the presence of an equivalent amount of caustic alkali. In the first case $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}$ fell from 62.37 to 40.02°, but in the second case there was a slight increase, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}$ being 63.69°. It appears that the ionisation of an active carboxylic acid leads to a smaller change in rotatory power than the ionisation of an active base.

The rotatory powers of these compounds have been determined in three solvents, *i.e.*, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone. The

¹ *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2410.
¹*ibid.*, 1925, 1996.

² *ibid.*, 1930, 1201.

³ *ibid.*, 1927, 1995.

4'-dimethylamino acid shows simple dispersion as by plotting $\frac{1}{\alpha}$ against λ^2 , exact straight lines are obtained, but the rotatory dispersion of 2'-dimethylaminocamphorophenylimide is complex in all the three solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Camphoric Anhydride with Aminodimethylanilines.—Camphoric anhydride and the amine (equal mols.) were heated together with a little fused sodium acetate in an oil-bath at 125-130° for 3 hours. The product was dissolved in alcohol and precipitated with water, when dark grey solid was precipitated. It was extracted with dilute solution of caustic soda to remove any imide formed. The filtered solution was then acidified with acetic acid till a slight turbidity was produced. It was kept overnight when a grey colouring matter settled. It was removed by filtration through a double filter paper and the filtrate was acidified. The solid mass, thus obtained, was crystallised from alcohol.

4'-Dimethylaminocamphoranilic Acid was crystallised from alcohol in white microcrystalline mass, m.p. 193° after darkening at 187°. It is soluble in the usual organic solvents but insoluble in benzene and water. (Found: N, 9·07. $C_{18}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8·80 per cent).

3'-Dimethylaminocamphoranilic Acid.—All attempts to crystallise it were unsuccessful. It was, therefore, purified by repeated dissolution in alkali and precipitation with an acid. It was obtained as a greyish white amorphous mass, darkening at 90°, shrinking at 100° and melting at 120°. (Found: N, 9·0. $C_{18}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8·80 per cent).

2'-Dimethylaminocamphoranilic Acid was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 152-53°. (Found: N, 9·0. $C_{18}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8·80 per cent).

Camphoro-o-dimethylaminophenylimide.—The residue left on the filter paper after treatment with dilute ammonia was crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) as microcrystalline powder, m.p. 149°. (Found: N, 9·45. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9·33 per cent).

TABLE III.

*Specific rotations.**4'-Dimethylaminocamphoranitic Acid.*

	Conc./25 cc.	$[\alpha]_D$	$[\alpha]_{5780}$	$[\alpha]_{5461}$	$[\alpha]_{4364}$
MeOH	0.2005 g.	69.82°	74.81°	92.26°	183.28°
EtOH	0.2004	62.37	66.11	78.59	158.43
Me ₂ CO	0.1999	54.44	55.65	68.78	137.00

3'-Dimethylaminocamphoranitic Acid.

MeOH	0.2510	55.7	59.7	66.7
EtOH	0.2015	37.8	39.0	49.0
Me ₂ CO	0.2525	27.7	34.6	39.6

2'-Dimethylaminocamphoranitic Acid.

MeOH	0.2005	0	6.2	8.72	18.7
EtOH	0.3004	0	0	0	18.0
Me ₂ CO	0.2006	-9.97	-16.82	-17.44	-22.43

Camphoro-o-dimethylaminophenylimide.

MeOH	0.2003	14.35	17.47	26.83	43.68
EtOH	0.2005	11.22	14.34	21.82	39.90
Me ₂ CO	0.2530	23.7	27.7	41.5	56.8

The readings were taken in a 2 dcm. tube and the temperature during all these readings was 25-26°.